

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF TEXTILE COMPOSITE UNIT CELLS USING CONVENTIONAL AND NOVEL TECHNIQUES

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SUMMARY: Although finite element (FE) analysis of the repeating unit cell of textile composites has received much attention in recent years, there remains considerable difficulty in the generation of appropriate FE models. There is a clear need for techniques of model generation which employ a high degree of automation if this type of analysis is to become more user-friendly and a routine part of the design process. In this paper, two techniques are described: 'conventional' FE modelling of the unit cell geometry, and a voxel-type approach known as the Grid Average method. Both techniques are driven using the TexGen solid modeller, through which a considerable proportion of the work may be automated. A simple damage model is incorporated, and stress-strain curves are generated with each technique for composite unit cells. These are compared with experimental measurements where available. It is noted that conventional FE modelling of some reinforcement architectures is not practical due to difficulties in mesh generation, but in these cases a solution can be obtained using the Grid Average method.

KEYWORDS: meso-scale modelling, textiles, Grid Average technique, stiffness, strength, damage prediction, residual stress

INTRODUCTION

The use of textile reinforcements in polymer composite components has become common, but the prediction of mechanical properties remains an area of considerable investigation. A number of analytical methods have been proposed for stiffness prediction, frequently based on averaging of local stiffnesses or compliances, e.g. [1-4], where a uniform stress or strain field is assumed. Some of these methods have also been extended to predict strength (e.g. [5-7]). Many such models are one-dimensional (e.g. [1]), predicting only axial properties. Others extend to two dimensions [2], considering the undulations of transverse tows, and have been extended to consider off-axis loading [8]. Although Hofstee [4] considered off-axis loading and non-orthogonal weaves (i.e. sheared fabrics), little work on failure prediction was undertaken. Aside from these limitations, one of the problems surrounding such analytical approaches is the complexity in adaptation to different weave styles, and moreover that they are based on idealised geometries, such that the effects of irregularities and variability cannot be investigated easily.

More generality is afforded by the use of FE models of the representative unit cell, a practice pioneered more than ten years ago [9]. Woo and Whitcomb also extended their work to

predict failure of woven composites [10], but they observed difficulties in finding a fully converged solution, despite using a fine mesh of well-formed finite elements. Since this work, many authors have attempted to use the FE method to model textile composites. Notable examples include Carvelli and Poggi [11], who have employed a two-scale technique incorporating micro-scale FE analysis of the fibre and matrix in order to determine properties of the impregnated tow for use in subsequent meso-scale analysis of the fabric repeating unit. Employing the WiseTex geometric model, Ivanov et al [12] demonstrated analysis of fabrics, including those with in-plane shear deformation. Both of these studies appeared to show limitations in the meshing process, either in the amount of manual intervention required or in the mesh quality which could be obtained. These problems are typical of the unit cell FE technique. Various methods have been proposed in the literature to address this issue. For example, Sun et al [13] suggested the use of p-type finite elements, which use higher order interpolation functions, allowing the use of meshes which would normally be considered to be of poor quality. Cox et al [14] proposed a method using three-dimensional ‘effective medium’ elements, representing the transverse and shear properties of the composite, being overlaid with one-dimensional line elements to represent the axial tow structure. Zeng et al [15] proposed the use of inhomogeneous finite elements, enabling the use of a regular grid of elements, where material properties were specified at the integration points rather than for the whole element. Kim and Swan [16] presented a method in which a regular grid of three-dimensional elements, or voxels, was refined locally in order to provide a more accurate representation of the geometry, connecting ‘floating’ nodes using kinematic coupling constraints.

The purpose of the current work is to use conventional, established FE methods to improve understanding of parameters affecting the mechanical behaviour of textile composites and, working in parallel, to develop and validate an alternative method which can be used with minimal manual intervention. The development of a simple technique is essential if realistic design analysis is to be performed for real components, where fibre volume fraction and process-induced shear deformation change continuously over the geometry of the part. Such a tool is required to analyse numerous configurations of the unit cell with minimum intervention in order to build a bank of material property data appropriate to different areas of a component. This kind of analysis is not practical with any of the conventional FE techniques available presently. The use of FE methods also permits analysis of complex (e.g. biaxial) loading conditions which cannot be considered with most analytical techniques.

METHODS OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

Conventional FE modelling based on the TexGen geometric modeller

Automated interface between TexGen and FE software

The TexGen software package has been developed at the University of Nottingham as a research tool, and is described in detail elsewhere [17,18]. It has the capability to describe any textile, including 2D and 3D weaves, weft- and warp-knitted fabrics and non-crimp fabrics. It is possible to export a geometry which has been created using TexGen into the commercial standard ACIS format; this enables the geometry to be opened using a third-party mesh generation package. Presently, Gambit (the pre-processor for the Fluent CFD package) is used to generate solid meshes of tetrahedral elements, with opposite faces of the unit cell matched to enable application of periodic boundary conditions. Following mesh generation, the mesh is read back in to TexGen, where appropriate material properties and orientations are specified and a complete input deck is produced for analysis with the Abaqus FE package.

Boundary conditions

In order to simulate the nature of the unit cell, periodic boundary conditions are applied such that the cell is considered to be repeated infinitely in all directions. This assumption becomes invalid if geometric imperfections or irregularities are introduced; hence the present work is restricted to regular, or idealised, fabric structures, although this issue will be addressed in due course. The boundary conditions are such that each translational degree of freedom on a node is coupled to that on the corresponding node on the opposite face, using the *EQUATION option in Abaqus. A dummy node is connected to the system (also using *EQUATION), which is used to apply displacement boundary conditions to the model; the reaction force reported at this node is equivalent to the load applied to the system. One node at the centre of the model is constrained in all three degrees of freedom to prevent rigid body motion.

Material model

As part of the research into textile composites at the University of Nottingham, a simple material model to describe damage development has been implemented for the Abaqus FE package by Zhao et al [19]. The implementation employs a user-written Fortran subroutine which evaluates the maximum stress failure criterion (within the orthogonal tows) or the von Mises criterion (within the isotropic matrix) at each calculation point and reduces appropriate material stiffness parameters if failure is deemed to have occurred, according to the scheme proposed by Blacketter et al [20]. By using a non-linear solution procedure in the FE analysis, it is possible to determine the effective stress-strain behaviour of the unit cell.

Since most thermosetting polymer matrix systems undergo some shrinkage due to chemical and thermal effects during polymerisation, an analysis procedure to consider curing-induced residual stresses is also in development. Figure 1 shows the predicted stress-strain behaviour of a unidirectional glass fibre/epoxy system ($V_f=60\%$) under transverse tensile loading, based on material properties published in the World Wide Failure Exercise [21]. Stress-strain data are presented for the same material system when residual stress is neglected and when it is incorporated into the analysis. These preliminary results suggest that consideration of residual stresses may have a considerable effect on predicted composite mechanical behaviour, although the method has not been fully extended to the unit cell scale to date and presently operates at the fibre/matrix scale.

Figure 1 Predicted stress-strain behaviour of a unidirectional glass/epoxy composite, showing the change in behaviour observed when residual stresses due to polymerisation and thermal shrinkage are considered.

The Grid Average technique

Outline

As previously stated, one of the most significant problems associated with conventional FE modelling is the generation of meshes consisting of well-shaped elements which define the geometry accurately; this presents significant difficulties, particularly in the intricate matrix volume. The mesh must also be refined sufficiently to give an accurate solution, while being within the limits of practical computation. In practice, these constraints frequently mean that models of realistic textile composite unit cells cannot be meshed satisfactorily, or that doing so requires significant time and expertise. This illustrates the clear need for a technique which can be automated; hence the Grid Average method has been developed.

The basis of the Grid Average method is to divide a rectangular unit cell into a regular grid of square elements in the x-y plane. Using TexGen, the composition of each element is specified by taking through-thickness samples at the element centre. The data obtained from the samples are exported to a file from the TexGen package, whereupon they are read by a custom application which calculates material properties and generates an input file for the Abaqus FE code, giving various options regarding the choice of boundary conditions, micromechanics models and FE formulation (Figure 3b). The latter application is written such that the ability to batch process a number of models can be incorporated easily. It allows elements with thickness to be constructed to describe the unit cell. These elements may be layered shell elements or solid (continuum) elements, as shown for a 2x2 twill weave in Figure 2a. The latter offers a more detailed solution capable of considering out-of-plane behaviour, and is also able to handle material orientations with an out-of-plane component, unlike layered shells.

Legend for (b): Reduced (average) V_f Tow V_f Layered element

Figure 2 (a) Construction of a unit cell using a regular grid and contents of a single through-thickness 'sample'; (b) Representation of a subcell using five solid (continuum) finite elements of different types

To define the model with reasonable accuracy, layered solid elements may be used. Each of these elements may be comprised of a number of different material layers of arbitrary thickness; layer thicknesses in adjacent elements do not need to be coincident. However, the use of layered solid elements bears considerable computational expense (approx three times

that of homogeneous solids), and visualisation of quantities such as local stresses and strains is not possible with the Abaqus post-processor (Abaqus Viewer) for these elements. In order to address these issues, an averaging method has been adopted as a more efficient alternative. Using this method, elements comprising some thickness of tow and some thickness of matrix are assigned a single fibre volume fraction (V_f), calculated according to the proportions of tow and matrix present and the tow V_f . This gives rise to elements around the tow edges with lower V_f , as indicated in Figure 2b. For elements containing layers of two different tows (i.e. those elements near tow crossovers), layered elements are employed in order to handle the material orientations correctly. The Grid Average model is analysed using the same boundary conditions and material model as the conventional FE model described above. Figure 3a shows the elements with orthotropic properties in a Grid Average model of the same 2x2 twill weave fabric, and the fibre volume fractions assigned to each element. For issues of practicality, elements with reduced V_f are graded into discrete categories, the number of which may be selected by the user (Figure 3b). This method is similar to traditional voxel methods with the addition of a V_f averaging scheme to reduce discontinuity at the tow/matrix interface and maintain the correct overall proportions of fibre/matrix, and layered elements to handle voxels with multiple reinforcement orientations. Although the methodology is similar to that employed by Vandeurzen [22] and Prodromou [23], the use of a simple V_f averaging technique to define element properties for a commercial FE code affords an increased level of generality, and the opportunity to explore different element formulations, boundary conditions and material models with relative ease.

Figure 3 (a) Orthotropic elements in a Grid Average model of a 2x2 twill weave with fibre volume fractions ranging from 6.5% to 65%; (b) Options dialogue for customising the analysis procedure

Comparison of results

Since the Grid Average technique is based extensively on approximation, it requires validation by comparing results obtained using this method with those obtained using conventional FE and with experimental data. An E-glass plain weave reinforcement (Vetrotex RT600) was used previously [24] to manufacture test plaques by RTM using Reichhold Norpol 420-100 unsaturated polyester resin. Tensile specimens were produced and tested in the bias direction of the reinforcement, where stress-strain response was observed to be highly non-linear. A geometric model of this reinforcement was generated in TexGen but, due to limitations described above, it was not possible to generate a conventional FE mesh with the computing software and hardware available. A Grid Average model consisting of

4096 20-noded brick elements was analysed (approximately 40 minutes runtime), and the predicted stress-strain behaviour is presented alongside the experimental data in Figure 4a. The geometry is shown in Figure 4b. Figure 4a also shows the predicted behaviour obtained using classical laminate theory (CLT) and the maximum stress failure criterion, assuming a symmetric lay-up of homogeneous UD plies, i.e. neglecting tow waviness and gaps between tows. In both Grid Average and CLT approaches, the micromechanics models described by Murthy and Chamis [25] were used with the material data from Table 1 to calculate tow or ply elastic constants and strengths as a function of fibre volume fraction.

Figure 4 shows that the initial stiffness of the material is predicted very well by the Grid Average method, but that the failure stress is underestimated by a factor of four. Possible reasons for this are that process-induced residual stresses are ignored, and that artificial stress concentrations may be formed at the material boundaries. It is thought that the solution was converged, since a more refined Grid Average model (approx. 25000 elements) was analysed and exhibited very similar stress-strain behaviour. The causes of the low prediction of failure stress are the subject of further investigation, but incorporation of residual stress in the modelling procedure may change the results somewhat, as demonstrated for the fibre/matrix scale in Figure 1. Nonetheless, the accuracy of the stiffness prediction is encouraging. This is particularly significant when considering more complex structures, such as 3D-woven reinforcements, for which simple models such as CLT do not suffice. It is hoped that this automated, validated and fast model for stiffness prediction will be advantageous for such materials. Note that for elastic stiffness predictions, a single time increment is required, so the solution time would reduce to around one minute for a 4000 element model if this were the only goal.

Figure 4 (a) Stress-strain response of plain weave E-glass/polyester subjected to loading in the bias direction: experimental data (solid line), Grid Average method (short-dashed line), classical laminate theory (long-dashed line); (b) Geometric model of the reinforcement

Table 1 Mechanical properties of constituent materials

Property	Matrix (Reichhold Norpol 420-100 polyester)	E-glass
Young's modulus, E (GPa)	3.7	73
Poisson's ratio, ν	0.26	0.22
Ultimate tensile strength, σ_u (MPa)	70	2000

Since it was not possible to produce a conventional 3D FE model of the plain weave composite, a 2x2 twill weave geometry was used to enable direct comparison of the conventional and Grid Average techniques, since this possessed a more open weave structure which simplified the meshing process. The geometry is shown in Figure 2. Figure 5 shows

the stress-strain curve obtained using a conventional FE model of the 2x2 twill weave (solid line) compared with that obtained from the Grid Average method (dashed line). The conventional FE model was comprised of approximately 76000 10-noded tetrahedral elements (12 hours runtime), while the grid average model employed 4000 20-noded brick elements (40 minutes runtime); each model used 50 time increments. Once again, a more refined Grid Average model (22400 elements, 10 hours runtime) was analysed, which gave very similar stress-strain behaviour, suggesting that the solution was converged. In each case, the fibre volume fraction within the tows was assumed to be 65%, where the tows occupied 29% of the total cell volume, yielding 19% V_f overall; this value is significantly lower than would be expected in real materials, but was dictated by the geometry chosen to ease the conventional meshing process. As mentioned previously, the classical laminate theory (CLT) prediction in Figure 5 employs the maximum stress failure criterion and is based on an assumption of uniform V_f , ignoring out-of-plane tow waviness and gaps between tows. The results show that all three models predict the same behaviour within the elastic regime, and that the onset of failure occurs at similar stresses in both of the FE methods. However, the maximum stress reported by the Grid Average model is somewhat higher than that of conventional FE (28MPa compared with 20MPa). In both cases, predicted failure stress is significantly below that suggested by CLT and, although there is no comparable experimental data for this material, Figure 4 implies that the CLT approach should give a reasonable prediction for composites with 2D woven reinforcement. Causes of low strength predictions may include neglecting process-induced residual stress, as suggested by the data shown in Figure 1. It should also be noted that the material model does not presently incorporate differences between stiffness terms in tension and compression, which may have a significant effect for failure modes dominated by matrix cracking. For example, an orthotropic element in which the shear stress exceeds the shear strength presently has the transverse stiffness, E_{2new} reduced to $0.01 \times E_{2original}$ despite retaining its ability to withstand compressive loads. The effect of this has yet to be investigated.

Figure 5 Stress-strain response of 2x2 twill weave models subjected to loading in the bias direction: conventional FE (solid line), Grid Average method (short-dashed line) and classical laminate theory in conjunction with max. stress failure criterion (long-dashed line)

Further similarity between the conventional and Grid Average models can be observed in Figure 6, which shows the areas of damage growth in each case, i.e. elements in which the calculated stress has exceeded the material strength. It is evident that in both models, damage is primarily located in the orthotropic (tow) regions. This finding is difficult to validate experimentally since real composites are unlikely to contain resin regions through the full

laminate thickness, but it does serve to demonstrate the capabilities of the Grid Average technique compared with the more time consuming conventional FE.

Figure 6 Damage present in FE models of 2x2 twill weave reinforced composite unit cell after application of 1% global strain in 1-direction. Red areas have reduced stiffness due to failure stress being exceeded, blue areas are undamaged. (a) Conventional FE model (64000 10-noded tetrahedral elements); (b) Grid Average model (4000 20-noded brick elements). White areas are multi-layered elements which cannot display contoured results using Abaqus.

CONCLUSIONS

Finite element techniques have been used to study three-dimensional models of textile reinforced composite unit cells. Results are presented from both conventional unit cell FE and a voxel-based method known as the Grid Average technique, both employing a simple damage model based on Blacketter's stiffness reduction scheme [20]. Comparisons with experimental data for a plain weave reinforced composite, tested in the bias direction, suggest that the stiffness prediction of the Grid Average technique is good, but that strength is underestimated significantly; the reasons for this are still under investigation, but preliminary results from a model incorporating residual stress due to curing suggest that this may have a significant effect on the results. Since it was not possible to produce a model of the realistic geometry using conventional FE, a geometry with an open weave structure was used to compare the two modelling techniques. Stiffness predictions from both models agreed well with those of CLT, although the predicted onset of failure occurred at much lower applied stresses, as observed for the plain weave geometry. Further experimental validation is required, but from the data presently available it appears that the Grid Average technique is suitable for stiffness prediction. Principal advantages of this method over conventional unit cell FE are that models can be generated automatically and in large numbers for parametric studies, that solution time is greatly reduced, and that it is possible to model closely-woven structures for which generation of traditional FE meshes proves to be a significant problem. Advantages compared with analytical techniques are the ability to determine a full three-dimensional stiffness matrix, to analyse more complex (e.g. 3D woven or 3D braided) reinforcement architectures and to consider arbitrary (e.g. biaxial) loading conditions. It is hoped that, with further investigation and development, the Grid Average technique will be capable of failure and damage prediction. It is thought that incorporation of process-induced residual stresses may have a significant effect on the failure predictions; implementation of this stage of the work is in progress.

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